

PRACTICAL ISSUES OF IMPOSING PROPERTY LIABILITY ON THE GOVERNING BODIES OF JOINT- STOCK COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

This thesis analyzes issues related to the liability of governing bodies in ensuring the effectiveness of corporate governance in joint-stock companies under the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Law “On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders’ Rights,” the legal grounds for holding governing bodies liable are examined. In addition, the thesis provides a practical assessment of the introduction of the institution of fiduciary duties and fiduciary liability of governing bodies of joint-stock companies following legislative amendments adopted in 2025. Based on the results of the analysis, the necessity of adopting a resolution by the Plenum of the Supreme Court to establish uniform judicial practice in corporate disputes is emphasized.

In the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the liability of governing bodies plays a significant role in ensuring the effectiveness of corporate governance in joint-stock companies. The liability of governing bodies is primarily aimed at protecting the interests of the company and its shareholders, ensuring compliance with legislation, and establishing transparent governance.

Under national legislation, members of governing bodies may be held liable under the following types of liability:

Civil liability – members of governing bodies are liable for damage caused to the company as a result of abuse of authority, negligence, or unlawful actions. In such cases, they are obliged to compensate for the material damage incurred.

Administrative liability – administrative sanctions are applied for violations of legal requirements in the activities of joint-stock companies, particularly those related to corporate governance, reporting, and information disclosure.

Criminal liability – if the actions of members of governing bodies contain elements of crimes such as fraud, abuse of official authority, embezzlement, or misappropriation of property, they may be subject to criminal liability.

Disciplinary liability – executive body managers and employees may be subject to measures such as warnings, reprimands, or dismissal in accordance with labor legislation.

This thesis primarily focuses on the practical analysis of civil (property) liability of governing bodies and identifies existing problems in law enforcement practice along with proposed solutions. The obligation and procedure for compensating material damage caused to a company are regulated by the civil legislation and laws governing joint-stock companies and protection of shareholders' rights in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to Article 45(3) of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a person who acts on behalf of a legal entity in accordance with the law or constituent documents must act honestly and reasonably in the interests of the legal entity. At the request of the founders (participants, members) of the legal entity, such a person is obliged to compensate for damage caused to the legal entity, unless otherwise provided by law or contract¹.

Professor M. Kamalov, analyzing the above provision, notes that the actions of members of the supervisory board and the head of the executive body of a joint-stock company must be carried out exclusively in the interests of the company and must be honest and reasonable².

Academic H. Rahmonkulov emphasizes that a person acting on behalf of a legal entity must pursue the goals of the legal entity and protect its interests using lawful means and methods to the best of their ability. He further notes that liability for violation of these requirements is expressed in the obligation to compensate for damage caused to the legal entity. The provisions on damage recovery are of a dispositive nature and may be modified or fully excluded not only by law but also by contract. If an employment contract is concluded between the legal entity and the individual acting on its behalf, the individual bears liability under labor law³.

In our view, while these provisions establish general grounds for holding governing bodies of joint-stock companies liable, the specific grounds for liability are set forth of Article 81(6) of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 6, 2014 "On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders' Rights".

According to this provision, a member of the supervisory board, director, member of the management board, or a trustee manager is liable for damage caused to the company as a result of:

- providing misleading or knowingly false information;
- violating the procedure for information disclosure established by the Law;
- proposing the conclusion of major transactions and/or transactions involving a conflict of interest that resulted in damage to the company, including transactions proposed for the purpose of obtaining benefits (income) for themselves or their affiliated persons⁴.

Furthermore, pursuant to Article 1 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 27, 2025 "On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the

¹ **Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan**, <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/111189>

² **Kamalov, M.** Liability of the Governing Bodies of a Joint-Stock Company. *Tashkent State University of Law*, Tashkent, 100047, Uzbekistan. *Yuridik Fanlar Axborotnomasi – Review of Law Sciences*, No. 3 (2018), pp. 108–111.

³ **Rahmonkulov, H.R. et al.** Commentary on the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Volume 1 (General Part). Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent: *VEKTOR PRESS*, 2010. 816 p. (Professional Commentaries), pp. 193, 124–125.

⁴ **Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan** of May 6, 2014 "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan 'On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders' Rights'", <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/2382409>

Republic of Uzbekistan,” Article 81(6) was supplemented with a new paragraph providing for liability for:

failure to fulfill fiduciary duties⁵.

This law introduced into national legislation the institution of fiduciary liability of governing bodies, defining the scope of fiduciary duties and the grounds for compensation of damage caused by their breach.

The grounds for criminal and administrative liability of officials of joint-stock companies are established by the Criminal Code and the Code of Administrative Liability of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Criminal Code defines the concept of an “official” as a person who, on a permanent, temporary, or special basis, performs the functions of a representative of authority or carries out organizational-administrative or administrative-economic functions in state bodies, self-governing bodies, enterprises, institutions, or organizations regardless of the form of ownership, and who is authorized to perform legally significant actions, including persons performing such functions in international organizations or foreign state bodies⁶.

Based on this definition, members of the governing bodies of joint-stock companies are considered officials under applicable civil and corporate legislation, the company charter, and internal regulations.

Professor M. Kamalov highlights that the legislator’s use of the term “official” in defining the liability of governing bodies is noteworthy, as this concept is broadly defined in legislation and includes members of supervisory boards and directors of both state-owned and private joint-stock companies⁷.

Some national professors (I. Zokirov⁸, U. Kholmiraev⁹, and others) argue that the liability of governing bodies for the obligations of business entities, including joint-stock companies, arises only as a result of the company’s insolvency and takes the form of subsidiary liability.

However, Article 81(6) of the Law on Joint-Stock Companies provides that governing bodies may be held liable not only for actions leading to insolvency but also for other damage caused to the company as a result of their culpable actions.

In our opinion, the key difference between this liability and subsidiary liability lies in the range of entities entitled to file a claim.

According to Article 81(4) of the Law, the company or a shareholder (or shareholders) holding at least one percent of the total issued shares has the right to bring a claim in court

⁵ **Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 27, 2025 “On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan”** <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/7862507>

⁶ **Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan**, Section Eight, Paragraph Nineteen (Legal Meaning of Terms), <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/111453>

⁷ **Kamalov, M.** Liability of the Governing Bodies of a Joint-Stock Company. *Tashkent State University of Law*, Tashkent, 100047, Uzbekistan. *Yuridik Fanlar Axborotnomasi – Review of Law Sciences*, No. 3 (2018), pp. 108–111.

⁸ **Zokirov, I.B.** Civil Law: Textbook. Part I. Responsible Editor: H. Rahmonkulov. Revised and expanded 5th edition. Tashkent: Publishing House of Tashkent State University of Law, 2009. 611 p.

⁹ **Kholmiraev, U.P.** Liability of Controlling Persons for the Obligations of Business Entities in National and Foreign Corporate Law. PhD Dissertation in Law. UDC: [347.7\(043.5\)\(575.1\)](#), pp. 116–122.

against a member of the supervisory board, director, member of the management board, or trustee manager for compensation of damage caused to the company¹⁰.

Nevertheless, these provisions are rarely applied in practice, giving rise to scholarly debate.

Recent amendments¹¹ to legislation on joint-stock companies aim to enhance the responsibility of governing bodies and majority shareholders to act honestly and reasonably in the interests of the company and other shareholders. The adoption of these amendments expanded the scope of obligations imposed on governing bodies.

However, one of the main practical problems in applying fiduciary duties is the lack of sufficient legal clarity regarding their content. Concepts such as “honesty,” “reasonableness,” and “priority of the company’s interests” are evaluative in nature, leading to differing judicial approaches and inconsistent court decisions in similar cases.

Another significant issue is the allocation of the burden of proof. In practice, the need for claimants—whether the company or minority shareholders—to prove the culpable actions of governing body members, the existence of damage, and causal connection significantly limits their ability to substantiate claims due to the complexity of proof.

Although minority shareholders holding at least one percent of shares are granted the right to file claims, this provision is rarely utilized in practice. The main reasons include high litigation costs, difficulties in evidence collection, limited access to corporate information, and corporate pressure.

These analyses demonstrate that improving legislation on joint-stock companies and protection of shareholders’ rights is closely linked to developing law enforcement skills and establishing consistent judicial practice.

Although current legislation provides for liability of governing bodies for damage caused, many provisions remain vague and difficult to apply in practice.

To address these issues, it is advisable to clarify fiduciary duties of governing bodies at the legislative level, define their content and limits, and introduce the **business judgment rule** for evaluating managerial decisions. Furthermore, it is necessary for the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan to adopt unified legal explanations on fiduciary liability, standards of proof, the range of eligible claimants, and methods for determining damages in corporate disputes in order to ensure consistent judicial practice.

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2. Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Section Eight, Paragraph Nineteen (Legal Meaning of Terms), <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/111453> (Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Жиноят кодекси, Саккизинчи бўлимнинг ўн тўққизинчи хатбошиси (Атамаларнинг

¹⁰ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 6, 2014 “On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan ‘On Joint-Stock Companies and Protection of Shareholders’ Rights”, <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/2382409>

¹¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 27, 2025 “On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan” <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/7862507>

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